

Review

A short overview of reinforced concrete frame structure design methodology and problems

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Abstract: Reinforced concrete frame structure is a kind of seismic, wind resistance performance which is a decent structure with flexible building layout. It uses space, good ductility and other characteristics that are not only can meet the requirements of building to set up a large room, but also can reduce the weight of the building. It is obvious that concrete frame structure is widely used in modern industrial and civil buildings. Considering to mind public safety, people's property, and so on, the norm concerning design of structures that can withstand progressive collapse should be adopted early. Nevertheless, keeping in mind the mechanical qualities of steel in building material and effectiveness of concrete is different from the performance of European nations. European and American rules may not be employed directly to the design of home building constructions. This study proposes a critical short demonstration about reinforced concrete frame structure design methodology and problems.

Keywords: Concrete structure, Building design, Bridge engineering, Concrete reinforcement structure design and analysis

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Introduction

Methodology short overview and problem description

The overall framework and methodology as well as problems of concrete reinforcement is shown in figure 1 below. One can get a full idea of reinforced concrete frame structure design problems and cautions as well as points that can be considered during structure design.

➤ The framework structure design requirements and problems

- (1) The force transmission route of the structure should be simple and clear. Under the action of load, the shorter and more direct the force transmission route of the structure, the higher its working efficiency will be, and the less building materials will be consumed.
- (2) Structural design should conform to mechanical laws. From the mechanical point of view, in the plane layout

of civil and public buildings, the column network should be arranged as far as possible in the way of equal span and equal depth (or approximately equal distance), which can reduce the distance between the side span columns accordingly, and can also make full use of the mechanical characteristics of continuous beams to reduce the bending moment in the structure.

Fig. 1: Basic Components and measures in concrete structure design

(3) Structural design should be combined with reality. The structural design should take into account the actual situation of engineering geology and the requirement of building function .

➤ **Second, in the concept design needs to pay attention to the problem**

1. Basic part. The basic design needs attention as follows.

- (1) When the width of the extended foundation under the column is wide, the foundation is uneven or the foundation is soft, it is appropriate to adopt the strip foundation under the column, and the unfavorable factor of bidirectional reuse of the foundation bottom area at the node should be considered to widen the foundation appropriately .
- (2) The construction area is good, and Party A should be advised to build the basement when the buried foundation depth is greater than 3m. When the bearing capacity of the foundation meets the design requirements, the basement bottom plate can no longer extend out to facilitate waterproof. A post pouring belt can be set every 30~40 m, and (2) indicate that two months after pouring with micro expansion concrete. When the basement exterior wall is concrete, the corresponding floor beam and foundation beam can be cancelled .
- (3) There are no seismic joints and expansion joints below the ground, and the joints should be strengthened. The wall foundation on both sides of the settlement joints must be separated.

2. Column part. The following questions should be considered when designing the column section.

- (1) In principle, the longitudinal reinforcement of the column should adopt large diameter and large spacing.

- (2) Because the longitudinal reinforcement of the beam anchors into the column, therefore, in general, only in the four corners of the column can it be conditional to bury the thicker pipe. When the pipe section area accounts for less than 4% of the column section, it is not necessary to check the calculation. No heating pipe should be worn inside the column.
- (3) The column should try to use high strength concrete to meet the limit of axial compression ratio, so as to reduce the section size.

3. Beam part. The following problems should be paid attention to when designing the beam part.

- (1) When the span of the external beam is not different, the beam is equal to the height, especially the external frame beam. When the size of the beam bottom from the top of the outer window is small, it is appropriate to increase the beam height to the top of the window. The outer frame beam should be as far as possible to make the outer skin flush with the column outer skin. The beam can also be slightly off the column edge, and the eccentricity of the two can be greater than 1/4 column width, but not more than 1/3 column width.
- (2) When there is a secondary beam on the beam, the secondary beam should be avoided to lap near the support of the main beam, otherwise the torsion resistance of the main beam caused by the secondary beam should be considered, and the measures such as increasing the structure of torsion resistance longitudinal bars and stirrups should be taken. When the cast plate is used, the torsional resistance problem is generally not serious.
- (3) When the end intersects with the frame beam or supports the secondary beam on the wall flexibly, the beam end support can be considered according to the simple support, but the beam end stirrup should be encrypted.

4. Cast plate part. The following problems should be paid attention to in the design of cast-in-place plate.

- (1) Plate reinforcement should be large diameter, large spacing, spacing is generally not less than 200 mm. Generally, the cracks of the board with span less than 6.6 m can meet the requirements. The spacing of steel bars above and below the plate should be equal, but the diameter type of steel bars can be different (and should not be too much). Several rooms connected with the same model, with the spacing of the bottom of the steel bar should be connected. Reinforcement calculation, to take into account the plastic internal force redistribution, will be multiplied by the plate reinforcement 0.8~0.9 reduction factor, will be multiplied by the plate reinforcement 1.1~1.2 amplification factor .
- (2) The negative reinforcement of the plate supporting on the outer ring frame beam should not be too large, otherwise it will produce too much additional torque on the beam.

➤ The treatment measures in the design

- (1) When building permission is granted, the section size of the column should be made larger as far as possible, so that the linear stiffness ratio of the column and beam is greater than 1 as far as possible, and the axial compression ratio of the column should be controlled to increase ductility. When checking the bearing capacity of the section, the reinforcement structure of the column should be strengthened. The reinforcement of longitudinal tensile reinforcement at the end of the beam shall not be too high. Pay attention to the joint construction and let the plastic hinge move inward towards the beam span .
- (2) "Strong shear and weak bending" is an important principle to ensure the ductility of components and prevent brittle failure. It requires artificially increasing the shear capacity of each bearing component relative to its flexural capacity, so that these parts of the structure will not appear brittle shear failure when experiencing rare earthquakes.

➤ **Structural calculation problems**

- (1) Design the basic seismic acceleration value: When the seismic fortification intensity is 7 degrees, the design basic seismic acceleration values are respectively 0.1g and 0.15g; When the seismic fortification intensity is 8 degrees, the design basic seismic acceleration values are 0.2g and 0.3g respectively. This and "89 specification" big difference, should pay attention to. In the calculation, we should also pay attention to the division of seismic zone and select the correct design basic seismic acceleration value.
- (2) Structural period reduction factor: Due to the existence of the filled wall, the actual structural stiffness of the frame structure will be greater than the calculated stiffness, and the calculation period will be greater than the actual period, which will lead to the calculated seismic effect is small, so that the structure is unsafe, so it is very necessary to reduce the calculation period of the structure. The reduction factor can be selected according to the material and quantity of the filling wall, generally 0.7~0.9.
- (3) Beam stiffness amplification factor: The beam input models of SATWE or TAT and other calculation software are rectangular sections, which do not consider the increase in stiffness caused by the formation of T-shaped section of the floor slab, so that the calculated seismic shear force is small, which makes the structure unsafe. Therefore, the stiffness of the beam should be enlarged when calculating, and the amplification coefficient should be 2.0 for the middle beam and 1.5 for the side beam.

Conclusion

This paper proposes a short description and overview of concrete reinforcement structure and design methodologies as well as the problems. These structure design parameters and steps plays very important role in concrete structural design technology. One can get a fully short idea and overview from this study especially for concrete structure design in domestic and European countries. Consequently, we should apply the norms of other nations for reference and then enhance the experience from design of construction to resist increasing collapse also. Lastly, we should set adequate norms of resist increasing deterioration for our nation. Further research on concrete structure design and evaluation for specific building can be considered and explained in future study.

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